

MaxPy: An open-source Python package for programmatic construction and manipulation of MaxMSP patches

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ABSTRACT

MaxMSP is a visual programming language for creating interactive audiovisual media that has found great success as a flexible and accessible option for computer music. However, the visual interface requires manual object placement and connection, which can be inefficient. Automated patch editing is possible either by visual programming with the [thispatcher] object or text-based programming with the [js] object. However, these objects cannot automatically create and save new patches, and they operate at *run-time* only, requiring live input to trigger patch construction. There is no solution for automated creation of multiple patches at *compile-time*, such that the constructed patches do not contain their own constructors. To this end, we present MaxPy, an open-source Python package for programmatic construction and manipulation of MaxMSP patches. MaxPy replaces the manual actions of placing objects, connecting patchcords, and saving patch files with text-based Python functions, thus enabling dynamic, procedural, high-volume patch generation at *compile-time*. MaxPy also includes the ability to import existing patches, allowing users to move freely between text-based Python programming and visual programming with the Max GUI. MaxPy enables composers, programmers, and creators to explore expanded possibilities for complex, dynamic, and algorithmic patch construction through text-based Python programming of MaxMSP.

Author Keywords

MaxMSP, visual languages, automation, generation, metaprogramming

CCS Concepts

•Applied computing → Sound and music computing;

1. INTRODUCTION

Programming languages have long held foundational importance in sound synthesis and audio processing, driving the frontier of computer music. Both text-based languages like CSound [2] and SuperCollider [7] as well as visual programming languages like PureData [8] and MaxMSP [1] have given computer musicians many options for writing code. In particular, visual languages have allowed non-programmers to create complex computational artifacts with relative ease due to their accessible and intuitive interfaces.

However, the main drawback of visual languages is the amount of manual interaction required to create a program. In MaxMSP, objects and patchcords must be manually placed and connected, which becomes inefficient for large or complex patches. These manual actions can be automated with the [thispatcher] object, which takes message inputs to create, destroy, connect, or disconnect objects within the current patch. The [js] object also provides text-based programming control over [thispatcher] functionality.

These automations can be considered a limited form of *metaprogramming*, which refers to languages that enable the programmatic manipulation of other programs. In this case, Javascript is used to manipulate MaxMSP code, or MaxMSP code itself is used to manipulate MaxMSP code. However, neither [js] nor [thispatcher] can be used to create or save new patches, and neither allows for *compile-time* behavior that would enable patch construction to occur outside of MaxMSP.

In this paper, we introduce MaxPy, an open-source tool for true metaprogramming of MaxMSP using Python, enabling compile-time creation, editing, and saving of Max patches. Metaprogramming has found enormous success in traditional programming contexts, including C++11's `constexpr` [5], Template Haskell [9], and Scala macros [3]. Following the success of metaprogramming in other domains [6], we believe that MaxPy will empower new modes of interaction with visual programming languages for human-centered audio programming and computer-aided composition.

2. MOTIVATING EXAMPLE

We first consider a motivating example of generating patches from chess data. Given the Forsyth-Edwards Notation (FEN) for a particular board configuration, we want to 1) place an abstraction for each piece in play, 2) input their color and position coordinates as messages, and 3) connect their outputs to an [~ezdac] (Fig. 1).

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Figure 1: Example of chess-to-maxpatch generation.

Figure 2: Single-patch generation from chess data using [js]. This patch must be manually saved after each iteration.

Manually creating the patch shown in Fig. 1 is not difficult. However, generating new patches based on different configurations becomes challenging, as MaxMSP lacks automated control over creating and saving patch files. Parsing FEN strings, placing objects, and connecting patchcords can all be automated with [thispatcher] or [js], but saving each generated patch as a separate file requires manual input (Fig. 2). This tedious process scales poorly at high volumes: imagine generating a different patch for every state of every game in the Games of the Day Archive [4] from the past year. Without metaprogramming, such a task would be insurmountable. MaxPy thus offers an efficient solution for automated patch generation, especially at high volumes¹.

3. MAXPY USAGE

This section gives a basic, non-comprehensive overview of MaxPy usage. Most recent code and documentation can be found at <https://github.com/Barnard-PL-Labs/MaxPy>.

3.1 Creating An Empty Patch

To use MaxPy, we first import the library and instantiate a MaxPatch.

```
1 import maxpy as mp
2
3 patch = mp.MaxPatch()
```

When given no arguments, the default MaxPatch constructor creates an empty patch.

3.2 Creating and Placing Objects

We can use MaxPatch.place() to create and place multiple objects at once:

```
1 counter, button = patch.place(["counter",
2                               "button"])
```

Alternatively, we can first create a "floating" MaxObject and then place it in the MaxPatch:

```
1 counter_obj = mp.MaxObject("counter")
2 button_obj = mp.MaxObject("button")
3 patch.place([counter_obj, button_obj])
```

MaxPy currently supports all max/msp/jit objects from a vanilla MaxMSP installation. External MaxMSP package support is discussed in Sec. 5.

3.3 Object Arguments and Attributes

Arguments and attributes are specified in the object creation string:

```
1 patch.place(["counter 4 @carryflag 1"])
2
3 #or...
4 counter_obj = mp.MaxObject("counter 4
5                               @carryflag 1")
6 patch.place([counter_obj])
```

Common box attributes are specified during object creation:

```
1 counter_obj = mp.MaxObject("counter",
2                               ignoreclick=1)
```

¹Code for the [js] and MaxPy implementations can be found at <https://github.com/Barnard-PL-Labs/MaxPy/tree/main/examples/chess-paper-example>.

4.2 you are god

This experiential music game uses MaxPy as a bridge between Processing and MaxMSP to automatically edit an open patch, based on user input to Processing.

Figure 6: Screenshot from you are god.

In the game, the user places a series of circles and connects them with lines. Small dots then bounce back and forth along these lines, triggering each circle’s unique sound on impact (Fig. 6).

The patch generation for this game is fairly simple: create one synth voice for each dot, and connect them to trigger inputs and a signal output³.

Python is used as a bridge between Processing and MaxMSP (Fig. 7). Processing first uses OSC to communicate the number of dots to Python. Python then uses MaxPy to create that number of synth voices in a MaxPatch (Fig. 8). Finally, Processing uses OSC to trigger these newly loaded voices in MaxMSP.

Figure 7: Diagram of dataflow within you are god.

Figure 8: The MaxPy-generated abstraction [yag-voices], containing a variable number of voices connected to OSC triggers.

This game is a simple example of MaxPy’s possibilities as a bridge between MaxMSP and other input sources. MaxPy allows data processing and patch generation to occur outside of both MaxMSP and the input method, freeing up

³The MaxPy code can be found at <https://github.com/ryurongliu/you-are-god/blob/main/yag.ipynb>.

computational load on both ends. This is particularly useful for interfacing with embedded systems that have limited on-board memory but require significant data processing.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work we have presented MaxPy, an open-source Python package for metaprogramming in MaxMSP. In addition to the promising results so far, our initial experiments with MaxPy have yielded a number of areas for future work.

One of the attractions of MaxMSP is the ability for external developers to create their own Max objects. MaxPy can support these external objects, but the current importation process is inefficient. We are developing a streamlined way to import objects that will allow MaxPy contributors to add MaxPy support for external packages.

Another open issue is typechecking in MaxPy, which would check for illegal patchcords attempting to bridge incompatible datatypes. This would enable several potential applications of MaxPy, such as the generation of random patches or the creation of an NLP patch generator.

Finally, proper typechecking in MaxPy will likely stem from (or lead to) a definition of the formal semantics of MaxMSP. Unfortunately, the wide variety of MaxMSP objects makes it difficult to pin down such a definition, particularly when considering externally developed object packages that use custom datatypes. Defining a formal semantics of MaxMSP remains an ongoing effort.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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